

D1.1: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

TRANSFORM

Deliverable description

Deliverable:

D1.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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WP 1 – Coordination and Management

Concerned work package leader:

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PU: Public (must be available on the website)

CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CI: Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Statement of originality

This document has been elaborated by the authors following the guidelines for data management in Horizon 2020 documents.

Disclaimer

This report reflects only the authors' view. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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Summary.

The TRANSFORM Data Management Plan (DMP) is the Deliverable 1.1 (D1.1) from the coordination and support action (CSA), TRANSFORM project - grant agreement (GA) 872687. This deliverable introduces the first version of the DMP. The DMP describes the way in which the TRANSFORM consortium will manage the datasets that will emerge from the project, and how best practices in terms of metadata and archiving will be used to ensure that the data will be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) for other potential users. Furthermore, the DMP provides information about what datasets the consortium is aiming to preserve and in which format.

The DMP will allow these data to be aligned with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot, for which TRANSFORM opted in.

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1. Definitions and Acronyms.

AB	Advisory Board
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016 ¹)
Dataset	A grouping of data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DS	Data Set
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
Metadata	A description of data
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
S3	Smart Specialisation Strategy
SwafS	Science with and for Society

¹ "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" - European Commission, 2016

2. Introduction.

The scope of the first version of the TRANSFORM Data Management Plan (DMP) for the EU is to define key elements that will facilitate the potential reuse of the data collected and processed within the project. The DMP will ensure that this data will be findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR), in accordance with the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data pilot.

2.1. Project Background

The TRANSFORM project is funded by the European Commission under its Horizon 2020 programme Science with and for Society (SwafS). In TRANSFORM three European regions join forces and open up their R&I activities to co-create more responsible approaches to innovation. Lombardy in Italy, Brussels-Capital Region in Belgium and Catalonia in Spain are all leaders in experimenting new pathways for territorial development. TRANSFORM brings them together to design, test and disseminate three sound co-creation methodological frameworks (participatory research agenda setting; design for social innovation; and citizen science). These frameworks will be at the forefront of implementation of Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3). They provide approaches and application areas of responsible and accountable territorial development through new forms of local decision-making. They have also proven beneficial in aligning science, innovation and society, making R&D more responsive to citizens' needs, concerns and aspirations. The three initiatives will implement a mutual learning process within and beyond Europe, pairing with a parallel co-design exercise in Boston (Massachusetts, US). The work in these three clusters will support and increase co-creation and participatory processes within their R&I ecosystems, both building on existing regional commitments towards transformative opportunities and strengthen the opening effect on the organisations involved. Regional governments involved in TRANSFORM will reflect on, experiment with, learn from and adopt RRI approaches to their R&I policies and actions. Concrete examples of inclusive and sustainable territorial development will be attained, thus providing a set of reliable Policy Recommendations to transforming regional R&I ecosystems towards RRI. TRANSFORM will also be integrated into Strategic Roadmaps for the implementation of RRI within S3, addressed to S3 key players, for maximum benefit across all S3 Thematic Platforms.

2.2. Data Management Plan objectives

This document is the initial TRANSFORM Data Management Plan (DMP). The DMP identifies the datasets that will be generated and used during the project and defines each dataset's purpose and life cycle.

In accordance with Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020 (European Commission, 2016), the objectives of the DMP are:

- To identify the datasets that TRANSFORM will produce;
- To define how these datasets will be made 'FAIR' (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable);
- To define the allocation of resources (costs and responsibility) for data management during and after the project;
- To define procedures for data security (including data recovery as well as safe storage) during the project and for long term preservation.

The Deliverable 1.1 "Data management plan" is part of work package 1 "Coordination and Management", and has been developed following the Horizon 2020 guidelines, with additional guidelines from DMPonline as suggested by the European Commission. The DMP is intended to be a living document where information will be continuously added and revised as the implementation progresses.

As key element of sustainable data management, the DMP outlines what, and how, data will be collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards will be applied, whether data will be shared/made open access and also how data will be curated and preserved during and after the end of the project. It provides guidelines, answers to issues, and presents the approach that the TRANSFORM project will adopt with respect to the management and protection of data. Legal and ethical issues related to the project's collecting and/or processing of personal data are identified and practically considered, taking into consideration the different methods by which data are collected (interviews, online surveys, workshops, questionnaires, etc.).

An updated version of the Data Management Plan will be released if other kinds of data will be generated/collected, if changes in consortium policies or in consortium composition occur, and if any other external factors affect the validity of the present DMP.

With regards to personal data, the Consortium shall ensure that data on individuals are transmitted and used in a secure environment; that the use of the data complies with ethical and legal requirements (including signed informed consent and applicable data protection laws and EU regulation); and that the use of both existing and new data is agreed with the data owner/data provider. Data records containing personal data are managed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679).

The intended target for this DMP is primarily constituted by the project partners. This document should be read in conjunction with deliverables D8.1 and D8.2 (to be released on M6 of the project) which examine the use of the data in conjunction with the EU Data Protection Policy and the ethical use of

data, respectively; this document is therefore restricted purely to the procedures of the data management.

It is the responsibility of each partner to notify the coordinator of changes in the data they are collecting during the project.

3. Project Data.

3.1 Project Datasets

Dataset Name and Outline of Data	Institution in Charge	WP
DS_TRANSFORM_1_Project_Partner This dataset consists of consortium members	FGB	1
DS_TRANSFORM_2_Advisory_Board This dataset consists of Advisory Board members	SfC	2
DS_TRANSFORM_3_Regional_Think_Tanks This dataset consists of Regional Think Tank members	BEPart	2
DS_TRANSFORM_4_Stakeholder_Mapping_Lombardy This dataset consists of information about stakeholder and key networks relevant for RRI in Lombardy	FGB	2
DS_TRANSFORM_5_Stakeholder_Mapping_Catalonia This dataset consists of information about stakeholder and key networks relevant for RRI performance in Catalonia	SfC	2
DS_TRANSFORM_6_Stakeholder_Mapping_Brussels_Capital This dataset consists of information about stakeholder and key networks relevant for RRI in Brussels-Capital	BePart	2
DS_TRANSFORM_7_Participants_Research_Agenda_Setting_Lombardy This dataset consists of participants in the Research Agenda Setting Exercise to be carried out in Lombardy	FGB	3
DS_TRANSFORM_8_Outputs_Research_Agenda_Setting_Lombardy This dataset consists of the outputs of the Research Agenda Setting Exercise to be carried out in Lombardy	FGB	3

DS_TRANSFORM_9_Participants_Citizen_Science_Catalonia This dataset consists of participants in the Citizen Science projects to be set in Catalonia	SfC	4
DS_TRANSFORM_10_Participants_Outputs_Science_Catalonia This dataset consists of the outputs of the Citizen Science projects to be set in Catalonia	SfC	4
DS_TRANSFORM_11_Participants_Design_Thinking_Brussels_Capital This dataset consists of participants in the Design Thinking for Social Innovation processes to be held in Brussels-Capital	BEPart	5
DS_TRANSFORM_12_Outputs_Design_Thinking_Brussels_Capital This dataset consists of the outputs of the Design Thinking for Social Innovation processes to be held in Brussels-Capital	BEPart	5
DS_TRANSFORM_13_Communication This dataset consists of communication and dissemination materials.	AEIDL	6
DS_TRANSFORM_14_Evaluation_Impact_Assessment This dataset consists of data about Impact Assessment of the project	UiB	7

3.2 Data Summary

3.2.1 The purpose of the data collection/generation in TRANSFORM

The scope of the data collection and generation in TRANSFORM is to put in place, evaluate and disseminate three different sound methodologies of citizen engagement in three different regional settings.

3.2.2 The relation to the objectives of the project

Data collection from the three experiences of citizen engagement is necessary to fulfil the objectives of TRANSFORM, which aims to test methodologies and approaches of citizen engagement in R&I decision making in three different Regions in Europe. The data coming from the exercises will be useful

both to evaluate the soundness of the approaches explored in TRANSFORM and to enhance policy-making at regional level. In fact, the three Regions involved in the project will use and implement what will emerge from the citizen engagement approaches in concrete policy actions on R&I at regional level.

3.2.3 The types and formats of data generated/collected

Type of data:

Personal data (for members of consortium, AB e Think Tank – WP1-WP2):

- Name
- Affiliation
- Country
- Mailing address
- Professional background
- Job title
- Gender
- IP addresses
- Photo

Other data:

- Data from online questionnaires and survey (Lombardy Cluster – WP3)
- Data from workshops in person (Lombardy-WP3, Catalonia-WP4, Brussels-Capital-WP5)
- Data from interviews (for evaluation - WP7)

Formats of the data:

- Data and metadata will be requested, stored and transferred in comma-separated values CSV format.
- To facilitate the data exchange, MS Excel compatible files including comma separated and .xls(x) format will be also accepted.
- For statistical purposes, other formats include .sas7bdat (SAS), .RData (R), .SAV (SPSS), .mat (matlab).
- Where applicable data formats may be migrated when new technologies become available and are proved robust enough to ensure digital continuity and continued availability of data.

3.2.4 If existing data is being re-used

At this stage of the project, it is very likely that no existing data will be re-used.

3.2.5 The origin of the data

Origin of the data:

- Data from sign-up sheets at workshops
- Data from questionnaires
- Data submitted to surveys
- Data from interviews
- Personal data upon requests of the consortium
- Data collected as results of the participatory exercise

4. FAIR Data.

This section relies on the standard H2020 template for FAIR data (“Guidelines on FAIR Data management in Horizon 2020” - European Commission, 2016).

4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

4.1.1 Discoverability/identifiability of data (metadata provision)

All data will have an associated metadata document (stored as a .txt file) which describes key aspects of the data.

4.1.2 Naming conventions used

Event listings are stored in a central spreadsheet and individual events are assigned a unique identifier of the format [short name partner]_[date]

Project deliverables are assigned a unique identifier TRANSFORM_[number of Deliverable]_[date of submission], e.g. TRANSFORM_D1.1_30042020 (already submitted).

All files made publicly available reference TRANSFORM in their name, with the recommendation that the convention TRANSFORM_xxxxxxx_[date], where xxxxxxx is a meaningful short description of the file.

Photographs and audio/visual recordings are be named TRANSFORM_[event]_[date of event]_[description of event/photograph content, e.g. workshop/dinner/group meeting].

4.1.3 Approach towards search keyword

We provide search keywords for optimizing possibilities for re-use

4.1.4 Approach for clear versioning

Filenames will include creation date in YYYYMMDD format. Deliverable reports will have a data identification sheet and version log.

4.2 Making data openly accessible

4.2.1 Which data will be made openly available

The only data which will not be made openly accessible will be data which contains personally identifiable information (e.g. individual evaluation forms) and data underlines deliverables that are covered by confidentiality.

The personal data processed in the project are not made publicly accessible but kept closed and inaccessible to third parties.

4.2.2 How the data will be made available

Data will be available to all consortium partners via Zenodo (with the exception of individual questionnaires, which will be stored at each partner's premises). The access to Zenodo repository for TRANSFORM is restricted to project partners. Should other individuals wish to access the data for research purposes during the project, it will be openly shared on request.

4.2.3 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data

Data will be published using standard file formats (txt, pdf, csv etc.). All data will be accessed using standard tools. Software relevant to access the data would be made available, but it is not seen as being a requirement. Should it be needed we will provide the required open source to access and analyse the data.

4.2.4 Where data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

For the duration of the project, personal data will be stored on local secured server of the partner responsible of taking care of this. Data to be public are stored on Zenodo.

4.3 Making data interoperable

As the project progresses and data is identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP.

4.3.1 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards to be used to facilitate interoperability

In the project we use standard file formats as noted above. Every dataset will have standard Zenodo metadata.

4.4 Making data re-usable

4.4.1 How the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

CC Licenses will be used for all data to be preserved.

4.4.2 When the data will be made available for re-use

This section will be compiled throughout the course of the project, when we get more information on the datasets that are made available for TRANSFORM.

4.4.3 Whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project

All Personal Identifiable Information will be restricted to internal usage and not going to be shared with third parties. For shared information, standard format, open source software, and proper documentation will guarantee re-usability by third parties.

4.4.4 Data quality assurance processes

A quality assurance process will be pursued within the duration of the project.

4.4.5 Length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

10 years after the end of the project.

5. Allocation of Resources.

5.1 Costs for making TRANSFORM data FAIR

Cost for making data fair are estimated to be zero. Zenod is funded by the EU, which means archiving data in this repository will be free of charge. However, repositories of specific institutions will not be free. Consortium partners will use their own budgets to archive personal data in their own repositories.

5.2 Responsibilities for data management in the project

Each beneficiary leading Work Packages is responsible for preparing the datasets to make FAIR the data collected within its own activities, provided that FGB, as Project Coordinator is co-responsible for general coordination and supervision. Furthermore, consortium partners have the responsibility to make sure their activities are in line with all applicable local, government and international laws, regulations and guidelines.

6. Ethical Aspects.

Deliverables D8.1 and D8.2 cover the ethics requirements in connection with the main issues of data management within the project.

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